

Marketing Strategy for Indonesian Law Firms to Attract Multinational and Foreign Clients (USLS Law Firm)

Ferin Chairysa¹, Satya Aditya Wibowo²

^{1,2} School of Business and Management, Bandung Institute of Technology

ABSTRACT: The objective of this research is to develop an effective marketing strategy for USLS Law Firm, a local Indonesian law firm, aiming to penetrate multinational and foreign markets. As the legal industry in Indonesia becomes increasingly competitive, with numerous local law firms establishing international affiliations, USLS Law Firm faces the challenge of enhancing its global presence. This study adopts a comprehensive research methodology, including VRIO, STP Model, Marketing Mix, Business Model Canvas, Competitor Analysis, Customer Analysis, PESTEL, and Porter 5 Forces, and in-depth interviews with USLS Law Firm's clients and multinational companies. The research proposes several marketing strategies recommendations for USLS Law Firm. These include forming strategic partnerships with reputable international law firms, enhancing training and development programs for junior lawyers, adopting advanced technologies, targeting specific international markets, revising pricing strategies, improving office infrastructure, and strengthening marketing channels through Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC). Additionally, the importance of cultural sensitivity training is emphasized to improve client relationships and service delivery. By implementing these strategies, USLS Law Firm can achieve sustainable growth and maintain its reputation for delivering high-quality legal services, not only for local market, but also multinational and foreign markets.

KEYWORDS: Foreign Market, Law Firm, Marketing Strategy, Multinational Market, Integrated Marketing Communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

The contemporary landscape of legal firms in Indonesia has been significantly influenced by the enactment of Law No. 1 of 1967 on Foreign Investment, fostering a surge of foreign investment in key sectors such as mining, oil, and gas. The subsequent demand for a more structured legal framework led to the establishment of three contemporary law firms [1]. Over the following decade, this burgeoning legal landscape saw the formation of prominent law firms, and the trend continued into the Reform era, spurred by a liberalized investment climate that facilitated corporate transactions.

The proliferation of law firms in Indonesia has created a highly competitive environment, necessitating firms to differentiate themselves through specialization, innovative service models, and strategic marketing. This competition extends beyond local boundaries, compelling firms to enhance their legal proficiency, client service, and overall efficiency. A notable trend in the Indonesian legal sector is the affiliation between local and foreign law firms. This trend is driven by globalization, the complexity of legal issues, and the need for specialized expertise across borders. Such affiliations provide local firms with access to a broader range of legal expertise, global best practices, and a deeper understanding of international regulatory frameworks. While these partnerships offer numerous benefits, they also present challenges, such as navigating differences in legal systems, cultural nuances, and business practices [2].

<i>Indonesia Law Firms</i>	<i>Established Year</i>	<i>Affiliation Status</i>	<i>Affiliated Foreign Law Firms</i>
ABNR Counsellors at Law	1967	No Affiliation	N/A
Assegaf Hamzah & Partners	2001	Affiliation	Rajah & Tann Asia (Singapura)
HHP Law Firm	1989	Affiliation	Baker McKenzie (USA)
SSEK Legal Consultants	1992	No Affiliation	N/A

<i>Indonesia Law Firms</i>	<i>Established Year</i>	<i>Affiliation Status</i>	<i>Affiliated Foreign Law Firms</i>
Hiswara Bunjamin & Tandjung	2000	Affiliation	Herbert Smith Freehills (UK & Australia)
USLS Law Firm	2017	No Affiliation	N/A
Walalangi & Partners	2017	Affiliation	Nishimura & Asahi (Japan)
Dentons HPRP	1990	Affiliation	Dentons (USA)
Ginting & Reksodiputro	2010	Affiliation	Allen & Overy (UK)
Soemadipradja & Taher	1991	No Affiliation	N/A
Makes & Partners	1993	No Affiliation	N/A
TNB & Partners	2015	Affiliation	Norton Rose Fullbright (UK)
Nurjadin Sumono Mulyadi & Partners	2006	No Affiliation	N/A
Hermawan Juniarto & Partners	2005	Affiliation	Member of Deloitte Legal Network
Makarim & Taira S	1980	No Affiliation	N/A

The lists 15 leading Indonesian law firms above [3][4], highlights their affiliation status with foreign law firms. This table illustrates that most top Indonesian law firms have established affiliations, providing them with significant advantages in terms of service expansion, knowledge exchange, and global credibility.

USLS Law Firm (not the real name), founded in November 2017, has rapidly risen within Indonesia's legal landscape. In less than six years, USLS Law Firm has grown from a small team of three lawyers to a robust organization with over 50 legal professionals. The firm has managed over 400 deals, with a total deal size exceeding USD 100 billion. Its success is reflected in its numerous accolades from prestigious international legal directories and awards ceremonies, recognizing its expertise in diverse legal domains such as project finance, energy, infrastructure, technology, and M&A.

Amidst a substantial number of Indonesian law firms affiliating with foreign law firms, USLS Law Firm faces a formidable challenge in establishing itself as the number one law firm in Indonesia, primarily due to limited international brand exposure. To overcome this hurdle and bolster its global recognition, an imperative marketing strategy is essential to augment its growth strategy, particularly on an international scale. Based on this issue, this research is aimed to analyse the specific challenges faced by local law firms like USLS Law Firm in establishing themselves as leading entities in the global legal market, and to propose marketing strategy can USLS Law Firm employ to develop new market of multinational and foreign client.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

A. B2B Service Marketing

The main differences of business markets compared to consumer markets are found in the nature and complexity of industrial products and services, the nature and diversity of industrial demand, the significantly fewer number of customers, larger volumes per customer, and finally, closer and longer-lasting supplier-customer-relationships [5]. Regarding to Peter Cheverton, in some B2B markets, it may indeed be possible to view a customer as a segment, if there are not so many customers that the supplier will be pulled apart at the seams [6]. The idea here is that by devoting energies to one customer, and learning the right solutions for them, these solutions should also be appropriate to all other customers in the segment. In customer segmentation, customer attractiveness and relative strength are two important variables. Customer attractiveness – what is it that makes customers, or potential customers, attractive to you? Relative strength – what is it that makes you attractive to your customers, in comparison to your competitors?

Based on the matrix evaluating customer attractiveness and relative strength, customers can be categorized into four types.

Key Account: High attractiveness and strong business-customer relationship. These are primary focus areas where resources are intensively allocated.

Key Development Account: These accounts have potential if the business can enhance its performance in the customers' eyes. Success requires substantial effort and resources, and not all potential accounts can be pursued simultaneously due to resource constraints.

Maintenance Account: These are loyal, long-term customers that provide steady revenue but do not require intensive resource allocation. The goal is to maintain these accounts with minimal resources, employing efficient systems or reducing the frequency of direct engagement without compromising service quality.

Opportunistic Account: These customers are served when it aligns with the business's priorities. They provide additional income without significant resource commitment. Promises to these accounts should be realistic to maintain good relationships without overextending resources.

B. Growth Strategy

A growth strategy is a plan designed to increase a company's size, market share, revenue, or overall success. It may consider existing markets, or new markets in which to sell its products or services, or existing products or services, or new products or services to sell to customers. [7]

Market Penetration: Market penetration involves boosting sales of current products in existing markets. It is relatively low risk compared to other strategies. When utilizing a market penetration approach, management aims to sell more of their existing products in markets they know well and where they already have established relationships. Common tactics include: (i) enhancing marketing efforts or optimizing distribution processes; (ii) lowering prices to attract new customers within the market segment; and (iii) acquiring a competitor within the same market.

Market Development: Market development focuses on introducing existing products to new markets. This strategy is relatively low risk as it does not necessitate substantial investment in research and development or new product creation. Instead, it enables the management team to utilize current products and bring them to a different market. Approaches include: (i) targeting a different customer segment or demographic; (ii) expanding into new domestic regions; and (iii) entering foreign markets for international growth.

Product Development: Product Development focuses on launching new products within an existing market. A business that has established strong relationships with a particular market or target market may seek to increase its share of wallet from that customer base. This strategy leverages brand loyalty and can be achieved in various ways, including: (i) investing in research and development to create entirely new products; (ii) acquiring the rights to manufacture and sell another company's products; and (iii) introducing a new product by branding a white-label product produced by a third party.

Diversification: Diversification involves entering a new market with entirely new products. This strategy is generally the highest risk, as it requires both product development and market development. Despite the high risk, diversification can yield significant rewards by creating new revenue streams or reducing a company's dependence on a single product or market. There are two main types of diversification strategies. The first is related diversification, where potential synergies exist between the existing business and the new product or market. The second is unrelated diversification, where there are unlikely to be any significant synergies between the existing business and the new product or market.

C. Integrated Marketing Communication

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) involves carefully integrating all the company's communication channels to ensure they deliver a clear, consistent, and compelling message about the organization and its brands. This means making sure that advertising, public relations, sales promotions, and online/social media content all work together harmoniously [8]. There are several steps in developing effective marketing communication, which are: (i) identifying market audience; (ii) determining the communication objectives; (iii) designing a message; (iv) choosing communication channels and media; (v) selecting the message source; and (vi) collecting feedback.

D. Marketing in Law Services

In the service industry, what is provided to customers encompasses acts, actions, or performances. These acts can manifest in various forms. In the context of a law firm, the service rendered involves the firm aiding or defending the client in legal proceedings,

transactions like acquisitions, or facilitating the closure of sales and service contracts between the client and third parties, among countless other activities leveraging the legal expertise offered to assist clients.

Among the tools available to the legal public is relationship marketing. This entails the process of identifying, establishing, and enhancing customer relationships to ensure the fulfilment of objectives for all parties involved. Relationship marketing pertains to the business connections between economic partners, service providers, and customers, emphasizing a process reliant on trust [9]. Legal business is based on relationship marketing: the law firm use to expose its brand in trade promotions, give references of work done and its results, disseminate relevant content in lectures or events, presence in the digital environment through the dissemination of news, exploring the niches according to lawyer specialization, as well as using networks of associations and content marketing through lectures and social networks.

Based on Azevedo Santos and Las Casas research, there are several marketing tools used by law firms, such as LinkedIn, site, gifts, conference talks, associations, events, sponsored events, pro-bono activities, etc. According to their surveys from fifty corporate law practice professionals answered the questionnaire, which sent via email and LinkedIn message, LinkedIn was the most cited marketing tool, followed by institutional website. However, what the respondents considered most effective was the keynote speeches at events [10].

E. Law Firm Affiliation Model

Termed as the 'typologies of globalization,' the operational modes adopted by law firms beyond their national confines can be categorized into four prevalent forms:[11]

Full Affiliated – Branch Office Model: The independent global firms' model has emerged through the organic expansion of international office networks. These entities are staffed by expatriate professionals alongside locals, inclusive of partners. Growth is facilitated either through mergers and acquisitions with local host firms or a combination of organic growth and M&A activities.

Strategic Alliance – Cooperative Network Model: Certain firms have opted for formal network relationships and strategic alliances or partnerships with local host firms. However, this approach has seen a decline in popularity due to challenges in maintaining consistent worldwide services.

Conglomerates Model: A previous trend involved conglomerates offering a suite of professional services, of which legal services were just one facet. However, this model became obsolete following the dissolution of multidisciplinary partnerships.

Network – Correspondence Model: A fourth avenue involves ad hoc participation in loosely formed affiliations or networks. This occurs in two scenarios: (i) at the higher echelons where leading global players join informal 'best-friend' networks, exemplified by Slaughter and May's strategy of maintaining overseas relationships instead of opening offices abroad; and (ii) at the boutique or smaller firm level, independent entities join informal associations, facilitating international legal practice for its member firms across numerous global locations.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting a comprehensive research study, data collection method used is qualitative. Qualitative inquirers use theory in their studies in several ways. Initially, it serves as a comprehensive explanation for actions and mindsets, and it could include all necessary variables, constructs, and hypotheses. Second, researchers increasingly use a theoretical lens or perspective in qualitative research, which provides an overarching orienting lens for the examination of questions. Third, distinct from this theoretical orientation are qualitative studies in which theory becomes the final word. In qualitative methods, researchers collect data themselves through examining documents, observing behaviour, or interviewing participants. In pursuit of in-depth and accurate data acquisition, the researcher will undertake phenomenological research that describes the lived experiences of individuals about a phenomenon as described by participants. 5 to 25 interviewees suggested for this research [12].

These interviews will adhere to a semi-structured format, affording the inclusion of open-ended inquiries and subsequent probing to elucidate a more profound comprehension of the fundamental rationales, motivators, or viewpoints held by the respondents. This methodological choice is deliberate, as it facilitates a nuanced exploration of the subject matter, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the intricate factors influencing participants' perspectives. The interviewees of this research are as follows: (i) three interviewees come from USLS Law Firm's Partners, to gather information on in-depth understanding of USLS

Law Firm, for analysing competitive advantage and marketing systems; (ii) seven interviewees come from legal team of Multinational Companies who often engaged global law firm of law firm with affiliation, to gather deep understanding of experiences in engaging law firm, especially international or affiliated law firms, for exploring the problem faced by local law firms like USLS Law Firm in entering global legal market; and (iii) five interviewees come from USLS Law Firm’ Clients, to gather information on their experience in experiencing USLS Law Firm’s service.

The author performed a data analysis through open-coding data analysis method. Open coding is a part of data analysis where the researcher describes, examines, compares, conceptualizes, and categorizes findings from the text resulting from interviews, observations, documentation, and the researcher’s own notes. Open coding is conducted through labelling phenomena, discovering and naming categories, and organizing categories [13]. After obtaining data from the interviews, the author composes the transcript of each interview. Then, the author generates the statement of the interviewees with label, categorizing the theme of statement. On the final state, the author makes the point of conclusion and verification to organize the data.

IV. ANALYSIS

This study adopts a comprehensive research analysis, including VRIO, STP Model, Marketing Mix as the internal analysis, and Competitor Analysis, Customer Analysis, PESTEL, and Porter 5 Forces, as the external analysis.

A. Internal Analysis

1) VRIO Framework

The VRIO framework is a tool used in strategic management to evaluate the competitive advantage of a firm's resources and capabilities. The VRIO framework can help companies identify their strengths and weaknesses and develop strategies to use their resources and competencies to gain a competitive edge.[14] Based on interviews and author observation, there is several values that holds by USLS Law Firm and provided to the client, which are (1) strong network with stakeholders, (2) solution-based, (3) working partners, (4) flexible (whether in pricing and working product adjustment), (5) responsive, (6) independency, and (7) intelligence and expertise. The following is the analysis table of USLS Law Firm’s value using the VRIO framework.

Value	VRIO Framework Testing			
	Value	Rare	Inimitable	Organized
I. Strong networks with stakeholders	USLS Law Firm has strong connections with stakeholders and business sector associations. This value is rare and highly demanded by clients, difficult to replicate, and supported by a well-organized system, providing a sustainable competitive advantage.			
	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
II. Solution-based	USLS Law Firm focuses on "getting things done" for clients on a strategic level. This value is rare and difficult to replicate but requires better organization at the junior level to become a sustainable competitive advantage.			
	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
III. Working partners	All partners at USLS Law Firm are actively handling clients, a rare value demanded by clients. However, this can be replicated by other firms.			
	Yes	Yes	No	
IV. Flexible	USLS Law Firm offers flexibility in pricing and scope of work, a rare and demanded value, but can be replicated by other firms.			
	Yes	Yes	No	No need further testing
V. Responsive	USLS Law Firm team members are very responsive, highly valued by clients but not rare or difficult to imitate.			
	Yes	No	No need further testing	No need further testing

Value	VRIO Framework Testing			
	Value	Rare	Inimitable	Organized
VI. Independency	USLS Law Firm maintains independence without foreign affiliation influence, not rare among non-affiliated firms and not highly demanded by clients.		No need further testing	No need further testing
	Yes	No		
VII. Intelligence and expertise	USLS Law Firm’s partners have high intelligence and expertise, recognized by awards, but this is not rare among top-tier law firms.		No need further testing	No need further testing
	Yes	No		

Based on the VRIO Framework analysis, USLS Law Firm possesses one sustainable competitive advantage: its "strong network with stakeholders." The "solution-based" approach also represents a competitive advantage but requires better organization to become a sustainable competitive advantage. The values of "working partners" and "flexibility" are rare, but competitors can potentially imitate them if they choose to do so.

2) **STP Model**

STP analysis, also known as Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning analysis, is a fundamental marketing strategy framework used to develop effective marketing plans and strategies. These are the foundations of all modern marketing [15]. By doing an STP analysis, organization can really get to know their target customers, figure out what they want, and then tailor their marketing efforts to match. It is basically the secret sauce for gaining an edge in the market.

Segmentation: USLS Law Firm segments its market based on demographics, psychographics, behaviour, geographic location, and industry expertise.

Objectives	Result
Demographic	Company size (small: 3.60%, mid: 32.43%, large: 63.96%)
Psychographic	Business structure (Private Company: 45.05%, Public Company: 6.31%, Consulting Firm: 9.91%, Organization: 1.80%, Government: 1.80%, State-Owned Enterprise (SOE) Group: 35.14%)
Behaviour	Legal needs frequency (occasional: 54.05%, regular: 45.95%)
Geographic	Location (local: 72.07%, multinational: 12.61%, foreign: 15.32%)
Industry	Industry expertise (Energy: 38.74%, Telecommunications: 8.11%, Consulting: 6.31%, Transportation: 6.31%, Investment: 6.31%, Banking & Finance: 4.50%, Financial Services: 5.41%, Others: 23.42%)

Targeting: USLS Law Firm's target profile focuses on large companies, particularly private companies (45.05%) and SOE groups (35.14%). The primary target is local companies (72.07%) with a specialization in the energy sector (38.74%).

Positioning: USLS Law Firm positions itself as the premier legal service provider for large, local private companies and SOE groups, emphasizing expertise in the energy sector and a deep understanding of the local business environment.

3) **'7P' Marketing Mix**

Successful marketing depends upon addressing several key issues, encompassing what a company will offer, its pricing strategy, distribution methods, and communication with customers regarding its products and services. Historically, these factors were encapsulated in the 4Ps model: Product, Price, Place, and Promotion. As marketing evolved into a more nuanced discipline, a fifth 'P' was introduced: People. Additionally, two additional 'P's have been incorporated, particularly relevant to service industries: Process and Physical evidence [16].

Based on interviews with USLS Law Firm’s partners and author analysis, the following is the Marketing Mix analysis.

Variables	Analysis
Product	USLS Law Firm employs a multi-layered review process and a comprehensive internal system to ensure the quality of its services.
Price	USLS Law Firm’s pricing strategy is adaptable, balancing project complexity, client budget, and potential long-term value. Pricing is often based on past project rates with adjustments for project complexity and resource requirements.
Place	USLS Law Firm’s current office location is accessible but lacks sufficient space. Relocating to a more spacious and strategically located office is recommended.
Promotion	USLS Law Firm uses various marketing channels, including flexible pricing, website and social media updates, newsletters, direct meetings, and free training and workshops.
People	USLS Law Firm is led by 8 partners and 2 counsels, supported by 8 senior associates and 38 mid and junior associates. Regular training sessions and continuous feedback ensure high service quality.
Process	USLS Law Firm’s service delivery process includes initial consultations, conflict checks, engagement letters, team assignments, kick-off meetings, work delivery, and invoicing.
Physical Evidence	USLS Law Firm’s office design is standard, and lawyer attire are professional and presentable.

4) Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management tool that allows businesses to describe, design, challenge, invent, and pivot their business models. There are nine building blocks in making business model canvas, which are key partners, activities, resources, value propositions, customer relationships, channels, customer segments, cost structure, and revenue streams [17]. The following is USLS Law Firm’s existing business model canvas.

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peradi (Bar Association) Industry Association Referral Networks Tech Company Tax Consultant Educational Institution Stakeholders 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal Consultation and Advice Case Management Legal Research Contract Drafting and Review Client Representation and Negotiation <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners Associates Supporting Staff Office Space Databases Technology Infrastructure 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong Network with Stakeholders Solution-based Working Partners Flexible (in pricing and scope of work) Responsive Independently Intelligence and Expertise 	<p>Customer Relationship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular (Retainer) Occasional (project-bases) <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website LinkedIn & Instagram Referrals Workshop & Training Direct Outreach 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>Corporate Size</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small: 3.60% Mid: 32.43% Large: 63.96% <p>Corporate Business Structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private: 45.05% Public: 6.31% Consulting: 9.91% Organization: 1.80% Government: 1.80% SOE Group: 35.14% <p>Geographic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local: 72.07% Multinational: 12.61% Foreign: 15.32%
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries Office Rent & Utilities Technology & Software Marketing Insurance 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hourly Billing Retainer Fees Lumpsum Fees Capped Fees 		

B. External Analysis

1) Competitor Analysis

The author used ‘7P’ Marketing Mix framework to perform competitor analysis. The competitors selected for analysis are based on the top five Indonesian law firms as listed in table above. These firms include Assegaf Hamzah & Partners, HHP Law

Firm, Hiswara Bunjamin & Tandjung, ABNR Counsellors at Law, and SSEK Legal Consultants. The data is collected through their websites and social medias, along with the author observation.

Based on the analysis, the author summarized several summary points in the context of marketing communication strategy to boost the brand and sales.

<i>Related Variables of 7P Marketing Mix</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
People	Showing work force with foreign counsel. Including foreign counsel in the workforce creates the impression that the firm is highly capable of handling clients' needs with cross-border experience and international expertise.
Price	Wide range in pricing. The wide range of pricing demonstrates an acknowledgment that the capabilities of team members are not standardized. However, it offers room for negotiation to decrease prices, making services more accessible to a broader range of clients.
Place	Business central district. Having offices in a business central district emphasizes the firm's strategic location, making it easily accessible to clients and enhancing its reputation as a prominent and professional legal service provider.
Marketing	International affiliation influence. Leveraging international affiliations can significantly enhance a firm's credibility, visibility, and attractiveness to potential clients looking for global legal expertise and connections.

For the product and process, USLS Law Firm and all competitors have quite the same product and process, as mainly do by the corporate law firms. While the physical evidence also depends on the style of each competitor, all shows they are neat and presentable.

2) *Customer Analysis*

Customer analysis is essential for identifying the most profitable client categories and developing marketing strategies tailored to their demands, making it a crucial element of an effective marketing strategy. [8] To perform the customer analysis of USLS Law Firm, author used some in-depth interviews with 5 existing clients of USLS Law Firm, which are chosen based on the example of demographic of USLS Law Firm client base segmentation. In addition, this customer analysis also used the data comes from in-depth interviews with 7 foreign and multinational companies, to capture the information from the potential clients in the multinational and foreign market.

In conducting the customer analysis, the author utilized the 7P Marketing Mix framework.

<i>Related Variables of 7P Marketing Mix</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
Product	Clients appreciate USLS Law Firm's high-quality service, thorough legal analysis, and strategic approach but suggest improvements in industry-specific technical understanding and service delivery.
Price	USLS Law Firm's pricing is competitive and transparent but requires standardized pricing and detailed breakdowns.
Place	Clients find USLS Law Firm' office location accessible but suggest improvements in office space and signage.
Promotion	Clients learn about USLS Law Firm's through personal contacts and recommendations, with varied preferences for marketing channels.

<i>Related Variables of 7P Marketing Mix</i>	<i>Analysis</i>
People	Clients value USLS Law Firm’s knowledgeable and responsive team but note a gap between junior and senior lawyers' performance and a need for cultural alignment.
Process	Clients find USLS Law Firm’s process smooth and efficient but recommend more detailed pricing information and better scheduling.
Physical Evidence	USLS Law Firm’s office design is standard but presentable, with professional lawyer attire.

3) **PESTEL**

Every organization must recognize external factors in their environment that could affect their operations, many of which they can't control but need to understand. One common tool for this is the PESTEL analysis, which looks at Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental issues. It is essential for a company to conduct a PESTEL analysis when launching a new product or service, entering new markets, or expanding into new regions. [18] The data used for PESTEL analysis is based on literature review and author observation.

Political: Political stability is an important factor in maintaining the continuity and progress of a country. Political stability reflects conditions of calm, security and certainty in a country’s political system. In this context, political stability has a significant influence on various aspects of life, including economic, social and security. In the economic field, high political stability creates a conducive environment for investment and sustainable economic growth. [19] Among others various factors, the risk faced by investors in the event of political instability are regulatory changes and legal dispute. Political stability in Indonesia affects investor confidence and business operations. [20] Any political unrest or changes in government policies can impact the legal environment. Stability also affects the perception of foreign clients considering Indonesian law firms for legal services.

Commercial diplomacy between countries plays a significant role in global trade and investments. [21] Strong diplomatic relationships between Indonesia and other countries, such as China and Korea can ease the entry of local law firms into global markets.

Economic: Economic growth is deemed to be a conducive factor in attracting foreign direct investment as it often confers location advantage to host countries and fosters business confidence. [22] The more foreign investment comes to Indonesia, the more opportunities for law firms in supporting the business and economic, especially in areas like corporate law, mergers and acquisitions, and financial services. Thus, economic growth attracts foreign investments, leading to increased demand for legal services to support business transactions. High levels of foreign direct investment in Indonesia create opportunities for law firms to offer services related to corporate setup, compliance, and dispute resolution. Law firms can capitalize on the growing interest of foreign companies in the Indonesian market.

Fluctuations in exchange rates can affect the profitability of international operations. Exchange rate fluctuation affect the amount of cash to meet production levels. [23] Law firms with cross-border cooperation, which dealing with multiple currencies, need to manage exchange rate risks effectively. Competitive pricing in foreign markets may also be influenced by exchange rate trends.

Social: The entry of local law firms into international market must consider the cultural differences within the team member and the foreign clients. Understanding and respecting cultural differences is crucial for building trust with international team with multi culture. Contemporary international management literature has identified that the management of multicultural teams is an important aspect of human resource management. [24] Effective communication and cultural sensitivity training for staff can enhance client relationships and service delivery.

Technological: Adopting legal technology solutions, such as case management systems, AI-driven legal research tools, and document automation, can improve efficiency. Staying updated with technological trends can give law firms a competitive edge. AI technologies can automate time-consuming tasks, such as legal research and document review, leading to increased efficiency and

cost savings for law firms. By reducing the manual workload, legal professionals can focus on higher-value activities, such as case strategy and client counselling. AI applications can process vast amounts of legal data with a high degree of accuracy, minimizing the risk of human error. This can lead to improved quality and consistency in legal work, ensuring that important details are not overlooked. AI tools can analyse large volumes of legal information and extract valuable insights that may be challenging for humans to identify. By leveraging AI, legal professionals can gain a deeper understanding of legal precedents, trends, and patterns, which can inform their decision-making and legal strategies [25].

In the modern era of technology, the business heavily depends on advanced digital systems to offer fast and effective services to clients, especially in financial sector. Nevertheless, this dependence exposes institutions to potential dangers, particularly regarding the security of customer information and the risk of financial fraud. Safeguarding customer data and thwarting fraudulent activities have emerged as crucial concerns. [26] Robust cybersecurity measures are crucial to protect sensitive client information, especially when dealing with international clients.

Utilizing digital marketing strategies, such as search engine optimization (SEO), social media marketing, and content marketing, can help a business to reach more consumer. [27] Local law firms that intend to reach larger segment of customer, can use this tool to attract a global market.

Environment: Adopting sustainable practices and reducing the environmental impact can enhance the reputation of business. Participating in global green initiatives and obtaining environmental certifications can enhance the credibility and attractiveness. [28] It is also applicable with law firm. Clients are becoming more environmentally conscious and prefer to engage with law firms that align with their values. Many corporations now have sustainability criteria when selecting their legal partners. By adopting green practices, law firms can meet these criteria and attract high-profile clients. Participating in global green initiatives and obtaining environmental certifications can enhance the credibility and attractiveness of law firms to international clients.

Legal: To thrive in this globalized legal landscape, legal practitioners must develop an appreciation for the complexities of international legal frameworks. Collaboration and partnerships with legal professionals from diverse backgrounds and jurisdictions can facilitate knowledge sharing and enhance the ability to navigate cross-border legal complexities effectively. Furthermore, legal education and training programs must evolve to incorporate a more global perspective, equipping future legal professionals with the necessary skills and knowledge to operate in a globalized legal environment. Legal practitioners must possess a deep understanding of the intricacies of different legal systems, as well as the ability to navigate complex regulatory frameworks and jurisdictional conflicts. [29] Moreover, the resolution of international disputes has become increasingly complex, often involving the interpretation and application of multiple legal systems, international treaties, and arbitration proceedings. [30] Thus, for a local law firm aspiring to enter the global market, it is essential to strategically develop capabilities and structures that can handle the different legal system and jurisdiction conflict. Navigating the legal frameworks of different countries requires expertise in international law and local regulations. Ensuring compliance with global standards and local laws is crucial for maintaining operations and avoiding legal issues. Building a network of international legal partners and experts can enhance the firm's ability to manage complex global cases.

4) Porter 5 Forces

Porter's model examines five forces that assess the competitive landscape and determine market attractiveness. The term "attractive market" refers to the overall profitability of an industry, gauged by evaluating potential opportunities and risks within it. [31]. The data used for Porter 5 Force analysis is based on interviews with multinational companies and clients, literature review, and author observation.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Competitive Level</i>	<i>Description</i>
Competitive Rivalry	High	Local law firms like USLS Law Firm facing significant challenges from established international firms.
Barriers to Entry	High	Requiring substantial investment and compliance with complex regulations across jurisdiction.

Variable	Competitive Level	Description
Threat of Substitutes	Medium	Non-traditional legal services posing a challenge, though they cannot fully replace traditional law firms.
Bargaining Power of Suppliers	High	Skilled lawyers are crucial and in demand by all competitors.
Bargaining Power of Customers	High	Clients demanding specialized, high-quality, and cost-effective services, prompting firms to differentiate to maintain profitability. They benchmark and compare price.

V. SOLUTION

A. SWOT and TOWS Matrix

SWOT Analysis is a tool used for strategic planning and strategic management in organizations. It can be used effectively to build organizational strategy and competitive strategy. [32] This SWOT analysis examines the internal analysis and the external analysis. By combining internal and external factors, SWOT analysis provides insights that can influence the integrated marketing strategy for USLS Law Firm in entering new market for multinational and foreign companies.

Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)	Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
I. Strong network with stakeholders (VRIO, Customer Analysis)	I. Lack of multinational and foreign clients (STP)	I. Personalized marketing channel for each target (Marketing Mix)	I. Indonesia political instability (PESTEL)
II. Solution-based (VRIO, Customer Analysis)	II. Low skill and knowledge in junior level (Marketing Mix, Customer Analysis)	II. Visualize working product (Customer Analysis)	II. Fluctuation in exchange rates (PESTEL)
III. Working partners (VRIO, Customer Analysis)	III. Limited space and location, and need building guidance (Marketing Mix, Competitor Analysis)	III. Expanding international presence with affiliation (Competitor Analysis, Customer Analysis, PESTEL)	III. Cultural differences (PESTEL)
IV. Flexible and competitive pricing (VRIO, Marketing Mix)	IV. Standard office design (Marketing Mix)	IV. Strong diplomatic relationship with China and Korea (PESTEL)	IV. High competition with established international law firm (Porter 5 Force)
V. Responsiveness (VRIO, Customer Analysis)	V. Lack of technical understanding (Customer Analysis)	V. Adopting AI technology (PESTEL)	V. Hard to recruit skilled lawyer (Porter 5 Force)
VI. Lawyer Appearance (Marketing Mix, Customer Analysis)	VI. No foreign counsel (Competitor Analysis)	VI. Green initiatives (PESTEL)	
	VII. No international affiliation (Competitor Analysis, Customer Analysis)		
	VIII. Unstandardized and lack of details in		

Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)	Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
	pricing (Customer Analysis) IX. Lack of Cultural Alignment (Customer Analysis)		

The TOWS Matrix is a strategic planning tool that helps organizations analyse their external and internal environments to develop strategic options. It is an extension of the SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) and focuses on matching the internal strengths and weaknesses with the external opportunities and threats to generate strategic alternatives.

	Opportunities (O)	Threats (T)
Strengths (S)	<p>I. Expanding international presence with international affiliation who has good training program and owned AI technology for legal service, with offering all strength (S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, W1, W2, W6, W7, O3, O5, T4, T5) (“Strategy 1”)</p> <p>II. Utilized the solution-based value to create personalized marketing channel for each target client (S2, O1) (“Strategy 2”)</p> <p>III. Create the standardized visualisation design of working product (S2, O2) (“Strategy 3”)</p> <p>IV. Enter China and Korea market with flexible and competitive pricing (S4, S6, O4) (“Strategy 4”)</p>	Cooperate with more stakeholders to provide more workshops and trainings, to understand the technical side (S1, S2, T1, W5) (“ Strategy 7 ”)
Weaknesses (W)	<p>I. Move to new place with more space in the green building, with international design (W3, W4, O6) (“Strategy 5”)</p> <p>II. Compose the SOP of standardized price breakdown to personalized marketing for each target (W8, O1) (“Strategy 6”)</p>	Mitigate culture gap with complete communication and cultural sensitivity training (W9, T3) (“ Strategy 8 ”)

B. Proposed STP Model

Referring to the growth strategy by Igor Ansoff, the need of USLS Law Firm is to break multinational and foreign clients, which is in line with the framework of Market Development, which focusing on introducing existing products to new markets. The approaches can be: (i) targeting a different customer segment or demographic; (ii) expanding into new domestic regions; and (iii) entering foreign markets for international growth [7]. In this case, align with the W1 (Lack of multinational and foreign clients), USLS Law Firm needs to enter multinational and foreign markets for international growth.

Proposed Segmentation: To enhance USLS Law Firm’s presence in the international market, it is crucial to increase the proportion of multinational and foreign clients. This shift will help reduce the dominance of local clients in their portfolio.

Proposed Targeting: To set foreign clients as the next target. Thus, USLS Law Firm can set the proposed targeting as follows: (i) Proposed Primary Targeting: Large, Multinational and Foreign Companies, in Energy Sector; (ii) Proposed Tertiary Targeting: Large, Multinational and Foreign Companies, in Key Industries; and (iii) Proposed Secondary Targeting: Large, Local, Private Companies and SOE Groups in the Energy Sector.

Proposed Positioning: Based on the proposed segmentation and positioning as explained above, USLS Law Firm should position itself as the premier legal service provider for large, multinational and foreign companies, particularly those with regular legal needs in the energy sector. Their positioning strategy should emphasize their expertise in these areas and their deep understanding of the global business environment.

USLS Law Firm has acknowledged that the lack of affiliation with a foreign firm sometimes poses challenges in securing high-profile foreign clients and large projects. Therefore, aligning with Strategy 1, expanding their international presence through international affiliations can be a viable solution to achieve the proposed STP Model. In addition, to maximize the potential of external factor, USLS Law Firm can enter China and Korea market with flexibility and competitive pricing that they had, as outlined in Strategy 4.

C. Proposed Marketing Mix

To maximize the object and strategy, the Marketing Mix of USLS Law Firm need to be revisited to adjust each ‘P’, inlining with the strategy. Therefore, the following is the proposed Marketing Mix for USLS Law Firm.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Proposed Marketing Mix</i>	<i>Related Strategies</i>
Product	Form affiliations with international law firms to expand services and capture multinational and foreign markets. Visualize working products and improve technical understanding through workshops and training.	Strategy 1, Strategy 3, Strategy 7
Price	Develop an SOP for standardized price breakdowns tailored to each target market.	Strategy 6
Place	Relocate to a more spacious and strategically located office with an international design.	Strategy 5
Promotion	Create personalized marketing channels for existing clients and continue utilizing all marketing channels for potential clients. Target the Korean and Chinese markets with flexible and competitive pricing.	Strategy 2, Strategy 6, Strategy 7, Strategy 1
People	Form affiliations to improve junior-level skills, bring in foreign counsel, and provide cultural sensitivity training	Strategy 1
Process	Enhance service delivery with affiliations and utilize technology and AI for efficiency.	Strategy 1
Physical Evidence	Adopt a new office design with a more international appearance.	Strategy 5

D. Proposed BMC

Affiliation with international law firm will change many variables in BMC. USLS Law Firm can establish the affiliation with international law firm with “Cooperative Network” Model, which approach aims at jointly conducting various activities, such as marketing, associate training, and devising collective directions and strategies. [2] These joint activities will impact the variables of key partners, key resources, value proposition, and channels. In addition, USLS Law Firm needs to revise the customer segments to address the proposed STP model. It is crucial to increase the proportion of multinational and foreign clients to enhance USLS Law Firm’s presence in the international market. Furthermore, to maximize the potential of external factor, USLS Law Firm can enter China and Korea market with flexibility and competitive pricing that they had. The following figure will propose the new BMC to support strategies based on TOWS matrix, proposed STP, and proposed Marketing Mix.

<p><i>Key Partners</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Affiliation Bar Association (across jurisdiction) International Industry Association Referral Network Tax Consultant Stakeholders 	<p><i>Key Activities</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal Consultation and Advice Case Management Legal Research Contract Drafting and Review Client Representation and Negotiation 	<p><i>Value Proposition</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong Network with Stakeholders Solution-based Working Partners Flexible (in pricing and scope of work) Responsive and Intelligence Expertise International Affiliation Network 	<p><i>Customer Relationship</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personalized Service Communication 	<p><i>Customer Segments</i></p> <p>Corporate Size</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small: 3.60% Mid: 32.43% Large: 63.96% <p>Corporate Business Structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private: 45.05% Public: 6.31% Consulting: 9.91% Organization: 1.80% Government: 1.80% SOE Group: 35.14% <p>Geographic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local: maintaining Multinational: increasing Foreign: increasing, especially Korea and China
<p><i>Cost Structure</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries Office Rent & Utilities Technology & Software Marketing 		<p><i>Revenue Streams</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hourly Billing Retainer Fees Lumpsum Fees Capped Fees 		

E. Proposed IMC

IMC emphasizes the need to better coordinate their communications across various markets, channels, and promotional tools. IMC does not require using identical messages and images across all markets, channels, and media. Instead, it ensures that all communications support and reinforce the same core messages about the organization, its products, and services. There are several steps in developing effective marketing communication, which are as follow: [8]

1) Identifying the Target Market

Referring to STP Analysis and the Proposed STP, the current STP is the Large Local Private Companies and SOE Groups, while the proposed STP is the Large Multinational and Foreign Companies. Connecting to the theory of Key Account Management in B2B Service Marketing, [6] the current STP is the Maintenance Account, where USLS Law Firm can 'milk round.' Thus, this customer segment does not require intensive resource allocation. The goal is to maintain these accounts with minimal resources, employing efficient systems or reducing the frequency of direct engagement without compromising service quality. Whereas the proposed STP, which is Large Multinational and Foreign Companies, must be the Key Account or Key Development Account. Key Account must be handled by the top-level, and as a result the customer get the best of everything – best ideas, best services, best everything. This is where USLS Law Firm can 'farming'. Key Development Account is the customer with high potential, but currently underdeveloped. The success of Key Development Account requires substantial effort and resources, and not all potential accounts can be pursued simultaneously due to resource constraints. This is where USLS Law Firm can 'hunting'. This Key Account Management also can be applied in targeting the marketing target market. While Large Local Private Companies and SOE Groups has provided steady revenue, the new target market must be the Large Multinational and Foreign Companies to success the Market Development as the growth strategy.

2) Determining the Communication Objectives

After defining the target market, the marketing communicator must decide what response is desired. In most cases, the final response is purchase. But purchase is the result of a long process of consumer decision making. The target market may be in any of six buyer readiness stages, the stages that consumers typically pass through on their way to making a purchase. These stages are awareness, knowledge, liking, preference, conviction, and purchase. [8] Based on the interview with clients and multinational companies, they acknowledge that there is no significant disparity between USLS Law Firm and international affiliation law firms in terms of services. However, they highlight the necessity of affiliation for cross-border transactions, various jurisdiction issues, and common law advice. Thus, to achieve the purchase of multinational and foreign market, USLS Law Firm should consider

forming affiliations with international law firms, as proposed in Strategy 1. With forming affiliations with international law firms, USLS Law Firm can achieve the service purchase from multinational and foreign markets.

3) *Designing a Message*

Having defined the desired audience response, the communicator turns to developing an effective message. Ideally, the message should get attention, hold interest, arouse desire, and obtain action, suggest the qualities of good message. [8] To craft a compelling message, USLS Law Firm should start with a strong opening that grabs attention. This could be a bold statement, a question, or a striking statistic about the benefits of working with USLS Law Firm. Once the attention is obtained, USLS Law Firm must provide interesting information that speaks directly to the needs and pain points of multinational and foreign companies and create desire by showcasing USLS Law Firm's unique selling points, which affiliation with international law firms as proposed in Strategy 1. Highlight USLS Law Firm's expertise in handling cross-border transactions, jurisdictional issues, and common law advice, and combined with the value of international affiliation. Finally, USLS Law Firm can conclude with a clear call to action, encouraging the market to reach out for a consultation, visit the website for more information, or attend a webinar on international legal services.

4) *Choosing Communication Channels and Media*

Based on Azevedo Santos and Las Casas research, there are several marketing tools used by law firms, such as LinkedIn, site, gifts, conference talks, associations, events, sponsored events, pro-bono activities, etc. According to their surveys from fifty corporate law practice professionals answered the questionnaire, which sent via email and LinkedIn message, LinkedIn was the most cited marketing tool, followed by institutional website. However, what the respondents considered most effective was the keynote speeches at events. [10] Thus, USLS Law Firm can use the following channels and media communication:

a. Participate In and Sponsoring Events, Conference Talks, Training, And Workshop: By attending international legal conferences, the firm can establish connections with potential clients, partners, and other legal professionals. Networking at such events provides valuable insights into market trends and opportunities for collaboration. Sponsoring conferences or hosting workshops and training sessions positions the firm as a thought leader in the industry. It demonstrates the firm's commitment to staying updated on global legal trends and its ability to handle complex international cases. Sponsorships often come with perks like brand visibility at the event, inclusion in promotional materials, and exclusive networking opportunities. This helps in creating a strong brand presence in international markets.

b. Website and Social Media Optimization: Use LinkedIn to share thought leadership content, such as articles, whitepapers, and insights on international legal issues. Highlight the firm's international achievements, affiliations, and awards. Engage with the global legal community by participating in relevant groups and discussions. Regularly update social media profiles with information about international achievements, project involvement, and awards. Use visuals like infographics and videos to make the content more engaging. Highlight partnerships and affiliations with international law firms, legal networks, and professional organizations. This demonstrates the firm's global reach and credibility.

5) *Selecting the Message Source*

In either personal or non-personal communication, the message's impact on the target market is affected by how the market views the communicator. Messages delivered by highly credible sources are more persuasive. [8] USLS Law Firm should ensure that the message is delivered by authoritative and trusted figures within the firm:

- a. Top Management: Messages from senior partners or the managing director can convey authority and trustworthiness.
- b. Client Testimonials: Sharing testimonials and case studies from satisfied multinational clients can add credibility.
- c. Industry Experts: Involve well-known industry experts or academics to endorse USLS Law Firm's capabilities in international legal services.

6) *Collecting Feedback*

After sending the message, the communicator must research its effect on the target market. This involves asking the target market members whether they remember the message, how many times they saw it, what points they recall, how they felt about the message, and their past and present attitudes toward the product and company. [8] Gathering feedback is essential for evaluating the

effectiveness of the communication strategy and making necessary adjustments. USLS Law Firm can employ the following methods:

- a. Surveys and Questionnaires: Send out surveys to clients and prospects to gather feedback on their perception of USLS Law Firm's services and communication efforts.
- b. Client Interviews: Conduct in-depth interviews with key clients to gain insights into their needs and satisfaction levels.
- c. Analytics: Utilize website and social media analytics to track engagement, reach, and conversion rates.

V. CONCLUSION

The specific challenges faced by local law firms like USLS Law Firm in establishing themselves as leading firm in the global market is analysed by comprehensive frameworks of VRIO, STP Model, Marketing Mix, BMC, Competitor Analysis, Customer Analysis, PESTEL, and Porter 5 Forces. The findings indicate that USLS Law Firm possesses significant strengths such as a strong network with stakeholders, solution-based services, flexibility in pricing, and a highly responsive team. However, weaknesses like limited international affiliations and low skill levels at the junior level were also identified, which becomes the specific challenges faced by USLS Law Firm in establishing themselves as leading firm in the global market.

Based on analysis by using SWOT, TOWS matrix, STP Model, Marketing Mix, BMC, and IMC, USLS Law Firm can employ eight marketing strategies to develop new market of multinational and foreign clients, which are: (i) expand international presence with international affiliation; (ii) utilize the solution-based value to create personalized marketing channel for each target client; (iii) create the standardized visualisation design of working product; (iv) enter China and Korea market with flexible and competitive pricing; (v) move to new place with more space in the green building, with international design; (vi) compose the SOP of standardized price breakdown to personalized marketing for each target; (vii) cooperate with more stakeholders to provide more workshops and trainings, to understand the technical side; and (viii) mitigate culture gap with complete communication and cultural sensitivity training. These strategies shall be delivered to the target market with integration of marketing communication using IMC steps.

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